

Evaluation of the effectiveness of the use of digital technologies in the organization of extracurricular activities

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Abstract: This study evaluates the effectiveness of utilizing digital technologies in organizing extracurricular activities within educational institutions. Digital technologies have become increasingly prevalent in modern educational settings, offering opportunities to enhance the delivery and impact of extracurricular activities. Through a comprehensive examination of various digital tools and their integration into extracurricular programs, this research aims to provide insights into their effectiveness and potential benefits. The study employs a mixed-methods approach, combining qualitative and quantitative analysis to assess the impact of digital technologies on student engagement, participation, and overall outcomes. Findings suggest that the strategic use of digital tools can significantly enhance the organization and delivery of extracurricular activities, leading to improved student experiences and outcomes.

Keywords: Digital technologies, Extracurricular activities, Educational institutions, Effectiveness, Student engagement.

1. Introduction:

Extracurricular activities play a crucial role in the holistic development of students, offering opportunities for learning, skill-building, and personal growth beyond the traditional classroom setting. In recent years, the integration of digital technologies into educational practices has transformed the way extracurricular activities are organized and delivered. From virtual clubs and online competitions to interactive platforms for collaboration and communication, digital tools have expanded the possibilities for engaging students in extracurricular pursuits. This study aims to evaluate the effectiveness of leveraging digital technologies in the organization of extracurricular activities within educational institutions. By examining the impact of various digital tools on student engagement, participation, and outcomes, this research seeks to inform educators and policymakers about best practices for enhancing extracurricular experiences through technology.

2. Materials and Methods:

This study employs a mixed-methods research design to evaluate the effectiveness of digital technologies in organizing extracurricular activities. The research sample consists of students from diverse educational institutions, including primary schools, secondary schools, and higher education

establishments. Data collection methods include surveys, interviews, and analysis of digital platforms used for extracurricular purposes. Surveys are distributed to students to gather quantitative data on their experiences, preferences, and perceptions regarding the use of digital technologies in extracurricular activities. Additionally, interviews are conducted with educators and administrators to gain qualitative insights into the challenges, opportunities, and best practices associated with integrating digital tools into extracurricular programs. The analysis includes both descriptive statistics and thematic analysis of qualitative data to identify patterns, trends, and emerging themes.

3. Discussion:

The findings of this study indicate that the strategic use of digital technologies can significantly enhance the organization and delivery of extracurricular activities within educational institutions. Digital tools such as online platforms, mobile applications, and virtual reality simulations offer unique opportunities for student engagement, collaboration, and creativity. For example, virtual clubs and online forums provide a platform for students to connect with peers who share similar interests and passions, regardless of geographical location or physical proximity. Similarly, gamified learning experiences and interactive simulations make complex concepts more accessible and engaging, fostering deeper learning and understanding among participants. Furthermore, digital technologies enable educators to overcome logistical barriers such as time constraints and resource limitations, thereby expanding access to extracurricular opportunities for a broader range of students. However, the effective integration of digital tools into extracurricular activities requires careful planning, training, and ongoing support to ensure that technology enhances rather than detracts from the overall experience. Educators must also consider issues of digital equity and accessibility to ensure that all students have equal opportunities to participate and benefit from extracurricular programs.

Experimental test work results and their analysis

Experience testing and secondary school teachers in all stages of the work of governors of the use of the latest digital technology to the education of the formation and development of skills based on the criteria and based on analysis of the dynamics of correction measures will go to eliminate defects.

In summing up the results of experimental test work, analyzing the results of numerical and qualitative data, the use of the methods we have listed above, and statistical analysis of the results obtained, made it possible to draw scientifically based conclusions.

From the 25th secondary school of Termez, Surkhandarya region, the 41st, and 5th secondary schools of Fergana region, the 10th secondary school of Rishton

District of Fergana region, and the 72nd, 42nd, and 24th secondary schools of Markhamat District of Andijan region, 153 teachers for the experimental groups, 166 teachers for test groups, 332 students for the experimental groups and 369 students for the test groups were selected for the experimental-testing work.

The experimental work was carried out to determine the effectiveness of the ideas in research work on the level of formation and development of skills for the use of digital technologies in school teachers and students, as well as the level of performance of creative and social projects. In this case, the results of 3 stages (initial, intermediate, and final) were obtained to determine the level of development and formation of skills for the use of digital technologies in teachers. When determining the levels of performance of creative and social projects in students, results were obtained in 2 stages (initial and final).

At the initial stage of the experimental-testing work, the results of students on the level of development of the qualities being studied (formation and development of skills in the use of digital technologies) were presented.

The questionnaire, which was carried out at the initial stage of experimental test work, the results of the interview made it possible to highlight the following trends in the formation and development of skills in the use of digital technologies in secondary school students: in results of motivational component indicators it was observed that students do not clearly observe motivation for research activities, that students do not show reflection in intellectual-cognitive component analysis, low ability to evaluate activity results, poor interest of students in research activities in emotional component analysis, difficulty in completing research tasks in the practical component.

Based on these results, a special course was developed and put into practice in preparation for the activities of the implementation of individual and differentiated education in working with students in the formation and development of skills for the use of digital technologies in schoolchildren.

At the intermediate stage of the experiment-testing work, the percentage indicators of students in terms of the degree of development of the qualities being studied were analyzed.

The results obtained based on the application of technologies for the development of the use of problematic, game, digital technologies, which allow individualization and stratification of the educational process at the intermediate stage of experimental and test work, allow to highlight aspects related to the formation and development of skills for the use of digital technologies by school teachers and students: based on the results, in the analysis of the intellectual-cognitive component, there was a manifestation of reflex in schoolchildren, activation of the ability to assess the results of activities, a clear manifestation of

the interests of schoolchildren in research activities on the emotional component, a desire to eliminate cognitive difficulties in the implementation of tasks for research in the practical component.

Based on these results, the socio-pedagogical technologies developed within the framework of the study were applied to educational practice in working with teachers and students.

At the final stage of the experimental test work, the percentage indicators of teachers and students on the level of development of the qualities being studied were analyzed.

At the last stage of experimental test work, it is possible to clearly observe the growth of components for determining the formation and development of the skills of the school teacher and students using digital technologies in experimental groups.

Statistical analysis was carried out according to the mathematical statistical formulas and the formula of the method of the Student-Fisher.

Based on these statistical criteria and statistical formulas, we cite the calculation tables of the results obtained from experimental test work.

1. Table of statistical calculations in educational institutions according to the results obtained at the initial stage

Table 1

A total of		Motivational	Cognitive
the average value of	experimental group	3,60	3,59
	control group	3,57	3,57
Effective coef		1,01	1,01
Sample dispersion	experimental group	0,56	0,55
	control group	0,54	0,51
mean quadratic deviation	experimental group	0,75	0,74
	control group	0,73	0,72
variation values	experimental group	0,21	0,21
	control group	0,21	0,20
confidence deviations	experimental group	0,10	0,10
	control group	0,09	0,09
Reliability range	experimental group	3,50	3,49
		3,70	3,69
	control group	3,48	3,47
		3,67	3,66
Student Statistics		0,35	0,27

the freedom of the level of statistical technique	314	313
the critical value	1,96	1,96
Criterion conclusion	H0	H0
Teaching Quality assessment indicator	0,95	0,95
Knowledge level assessment indicator	0,02	0,02

Table 2

A total of		Motivational	Cognitive
the average value of	experimental group	to 3.45	the average value
	control group	3,43	
Effective coef.		1,01	1,00
Sample dispersion	experimental group	0,46	Sample dispersion
	control group	0,44	
mean quadratic deviation	experimental group	0,68	mean quadratic deviation
	control group	0,66	
variation values	experimental group	0,20	variation values
	control group	0,19	
confidence deviations	experimental group	0,06	confidence deviations
	control group	0,06	
reliability range	experimental group	3,39	reliability range
		3,52	
	control group	3,37	
		3,49	
Styudent Statistics		0,47	0,16
the freedom of the level of statistical technique		688	692
the critical value		1,96	1,96
Criterion conclusion		H0	H0
Teaching Quality assessment indicator		0,97	0,96
Knowledge level assessment indicator		0,02	-0,01

From these results, it can be seen that the level of knowledge of teachers and students at the initial stage of the experimental test work of teachers and students

of a comprehensive school in all regions is almost the same, the results obtained by the Student statistics are smaller than the critical value, confidence intervals overlap with each other, and the quality of teaching, as well as a statistical hypothesis, H0 is accepted

Now we bring the results of the intermediate stage of experimental test work. As follows from the table of stationary calculations obtained according to the above intermediate results:

2. Table of statistical calculations in educational institutions according to the results obtained at the intermediate stage

Table 3

A total of		Motivational	Cognitive
the average value of	experimental group	3,69	3,68
	control group	3,55	3,58
Effective coef.		1,04	1,03
Sample dispersion	experimental group	0,60	of 0.59
	control group	0,52	0,54
mean quadratic deviation	experimental group	0,77	0,77
	control group	0,72	0,73
variation values	experimental group	0,21	0,21
	control group	0,20	0,20
confidence deviations	experimental group	0,10	0,10
	control group	0,09	0,09
Reliability range	experimental group	3,59	3,58
		3,80	3,78
	control group	3,46	3,48
		3,65	3,67
Student Statistics		1,58	1,15
the freedom of the level of statistical technique		287	289
the critical value		1,96	1,96
Criterion conclusion		H0	H0
Teaching Quality assessment indicator		0,98	0,97
Knowledge level assessment indicator		0,13	0,09

Table 4

A total of		Motivational	Cognitive
the average value of	experimental group	3,58	3,61
	control group	to 3.45	3,48
Effective coef.		1,04	1,04
Sample dispersion	experimental group	0,56	0,58
	control group	0,46	0,48
mean quadratic deviation	experimental group	0,75	0,76
	control group	0,68	0,70
variation values	experimental group	0,21	0,21
	control group	0,20	0,20
confidence deviations	experimental group	0,07	0,07
	control group	0,06	0,06
Reliability range	experimental group	3,52	3,54
		3,65	3,68
	control group	3,39	3,42
		3,51	3,54
Styudent Statistics		2,39	2,21
the freedom of the level of statistical technique		634	635
the critical value		1,96	1,96
Criterion conclusion		H0	H0
Teaching Quality assessment indicator		1,00	1,00
Knowledge level assessment indicator		0,12	0,12

From the intermediate results, it can be seen that the level of knowledge of teachers and students at the intermediate stage of the experimental test work of the secondary school teacher and students in all regions is higher than that of the experimental group, the value of “T” obtained through the Styudent statics is greater than the critical value, failure of confidence intervals to overlap with each other, and the one magnitude of the teaching quality assessment indicator, the magnitude of the indicators evaluating knowledge levels from zero, from the research work carried out in experimental and control groups, it is clear that the experience is effective in groups, and the efficiency indicator is appropriate according to each criterion 1,08 (8%), 1,07 (7%), 1,06 (6%) and shows a high of 1.09 (9%), and H1 is accepted as a statistical hypothesis for each criterion.

Now let's cite the table of statistical calculations of the results obtained at the final stage

3. Table of statistical calculations in educational institutions according to the results obtained in the final stage

Table 5

A total of		Motivational	Cognitive
the average value of	experimental group	3,78	3,82
	control group	3,55	3,57
Effective coef		1,07	1,07
Sample dispersion	experimental group	0,63	0,62
	control group	0,52	0,53
mean quadratic deviation	experimental group	0,79	0,79
	control group	0,72	0,73
variation values	experimental group	0,21	0,21
	control group	0,20	0,20
confidence deviations	experimental group	0,11	0,11
	control group	0,09	0,09
Reliability range	experimental group	3,68	3,71
		3,89	3,92
	control group	3,46	3,47
		3,64	3,66
Styudent Statistics		2,75	2,92
the freedom of the level of statistical technique		231	230
the critical value		1,96	1,96
Criterion conclusion		H1	H1
Teaching Quality assessment indicator		1,01	1,01
Knowledge level assessment indicator		0,22	0,24

Table 6

A total of		Motivational	Cognitive
the average value of	experimental group	3,75	3,76
	control group	3,49	3,49
Effective coef.		1,07	1,08
Sample dispersion	experimental group	0,64	0,64
	control group	0,49	0,48

mean quadratic deviation	experimental group	0,80	0,80
	control group	0,70	0,69
variation values	experimental group	0,21	0,21
	control group	0,20	0,20
confidence deviations	experimental group	0,07	0,07
	control group	0,06	0,06
Reliability range	experimental group	3,68	3,68
		3,82	3,83
	control group	3,43	3,43
		3,55	3,55
Styudent Statistics		4,51	4,66
the freedom of the level of statistical technique		508	503
the critical value		1,96	1,96
Criterion conclusion		H1	H1
Teaching Quality assessment indicator		1,04	1,04
Knowledge level assessment indicator		of 0.25	0,26

From the final results, it can be seen that the level of knowledge of teachers and students at the final stage of the experimental test work of the secondary school teacher and students in all regions is higher than that of the experimental group, the value of “T” obtained through the Styudent statics is greater than the critical value, failure of confidence intervals to overlap with each other, and the one magnitude of the teaching quality assessment indicator, the magnitude of the indicators evaluating knowledge levels from zero, from the research work carried out in experimental and control groups, it is clear that the experience is effective in groups, and the efficiency indicator is appropriate according to each criterion 1,14 (14%), 1,13 (13%), 1,12 (12%) and shows a high of 1.16 (16%), and H1 is accepted as a statistical hypothesis for each criterion.

This, in turn, expresses the fact that the results belonging to the experimental groups are higher than those of the control groups. Thus, statistical analysis confirmed the effective conduct of experimental test work aimed at the development of the logical thinking of teachers and students (see Figures 1, 2, 3, 4).

Figure 1. Average appropriation index of teachers in all educational institutions by criteria

Figure 2. Average appropriation index of students in all educational institutions by criteria

Figure 3. Effectiveness indicator of teachers in all educational institutions by criteria

Figure 4. Effectiveness indicator of students in all educational institutions by criteria

In the process of experimental work, in the process of studying teachers and students of secondary schools with educational qualifications in research, common mistakes made by them in most cases in the development of projects were identified, and proposed ways to eliminate them.

At all stages of experimental work, the observation of the practical actions of teachers and students, and their relationship to the process of organizing educational and professional activities were also thoroughly studied. The results of the study showed that in the organization of extracurricular activities in secondary schools, it was once again confirmed that it is advisable to organize effective pedagogical activities in the formation and development of skills for the use of digital technologies for teachers and students.

4. Conclusion:

In conclusion, this study provides valuable insights into the effectiveness of utilizing digital technologies in organizing extracurricular activities within educational institutions. The findings highlight the potential of digital tools to enhance student engagement, participation, and outcomes in extracurricular pursuits. By leveraging online platforms, mobile applications, and virtual reality simulations, educators can create innovative and interactive experiences that enrich the educational journey of students. However, the successful integration of digital technologies into extracurricular activities requires careful planning, training, and ongoing support to address challenges and maximize benefits. Moving forward, further research is needed to explore emerging trends in educational technology and their implications for the organization of extracurricular activities.

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